

Short name	Societal challenges	Long name	Lack of social acceptance and acceptability of CC(U)S technology, particularly storage
Geographical scope	National and regional levels, issues identified in Denmark, the Baltic States, Germany; large uncertainties in other countries		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Lack of social acceptance has historically hindered the development of the technology and led to adverse regulatory action, not least in Germany and the Baltic States.</p> <p>Societal engagement with CC(U)S and knowledge of its importance for climate change mitigation is, in many countries, very limited and civil society organizations have actively lobbied against CC(U)S in the past, especially when CCS was presented as an option to decarbonize fossil fuel-based energy infrastructures.</p> <p>Low (climate change mitigation) benefit perception as most laypeople does not reflect on how the industry could be decarbonized and much public discourse focuses on more salient everyday behavioural measures such as recycling.</p> <p>Lack of knowledge of CC(U)S in general, and limited knowledge on differences between specific value-chains of CCS, CCU, CCUS, BECCS makes for a high level of abstraction (and a low level of perceived benefit).</p> <p>Low benefit perception can increase risk perceived (see the issue profile of risk and benefit perceptions).</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cancellation of projects in Finland, Germany, and the Netherlands • Challenge of authorities in Denmark with social acceptance • High degree of uncertainty in political commitments. • Uncertain status of some forms of CC(U) within policy instruments and limited advocacy for meaningful support. 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of compensation and/or support schemes for local communities. • The energy crisis as the aftermath of the Russian invasion of Ukraine might change the perception of the public • How to shift from social acceptance to social acceptability 		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Karimi, F., & Komendantova, N. (2017): Understanding experts' views and risk perceptions on carbon capture and storage in three European countries. <i>GeoJournal</i>, 82(1), 185–200. https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-015-9677-8 • Akerboom, S., Waldmann, S., Mukherjee, A., Agaton, C., Sanders, M., & Kramer, G. J. (2021): Different This Time? The Prospects of CCS in the Netherlands in the 2020s. <i>Frontiers in Energy Research</i>, 9, 193. https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2021.644796 		